

FINAL THOUGHTS ON REDUCING CRIME THROUGH MULTI-FACETED APPROACHES

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This study investigates the critical factors influencing criminal involvement, focusing on social, economic, and familial perspectives. It examines the upbringing conditions, peer relationships, and educational environments of convicts, alongside their economic status and family constraints. Utilizing standardized methodologies and expert consultations, the research aims to establish correlations between these variables and criminal behavior. The psychological attachment of convicts to their families is measured using the psychological family attachment scale developed by Seema Gul from women university, Peshawar. The findings contribute to understanding the multifaceted origins of crime and inform strategies for prevention and intervention.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past few decades, many societies have witnessed a concerning rise in crime and criminal involvement, suggesting an escalating trend in the likelihood of individuals engaging in criminal activities. While the motives behind such behaviors are vast and complex, this study aims to focus on several critical and generalizable factors that contribute to crime and criminal thought processes. To comprehensively understand criminal behavior, this research examines the interplay between social, economic, and familial perspectives of convicts. It analyzes how these factors shape individual trajectories towards crime, providing valuable insights into the broader social context. The study explores various dimensions, including upbringing conditions, peer influences, and educational environments, which are essential in shaping an individual's worldview and choices. The social framework encompasses discussions of familial

relationships, living environments, friendships, and shared ideologies among peers across various educational levels, from elementary to higher education.

In addition to the social aspects, economic factors are analyzed, including job status, salary ranges, and overall economic conditions faced by convicts. This includes examining the economic constraints of their immediate families, which can significantly impact their decisions and behaviors. Understanding the financial backgrounds and economic pressures experienced by these individuals is crucial in grasping the dynamics of their criminal involvement.

Furthermore, this study pays particular attention to the degree of psychological attachment that convicts maintain with their families. Utilizing the psychological family attachment scale developed by Seema Gul from women university, Peshawar, the

research quantitatively assesses the familial bonds that may influence criminal behavior. Through carefully chosen standardized methodologies and ongoing consultation with field experts, this study endeavors to establish correlations among the identified variables, seeking to contribute to the broader discourse on crime prevention and intervention. By unraveling the multifaceted origins of criminal behavior, this research aims to inform effective strategies that can mitigate crime and enhance community support systems

FINDINGS OF SIMPLE TABLE

Age of the respondent:

Findings of Simple Table		
Ages in Years	Frequency	Percentage
18 - 20	8	2.7
21 - 30	121	40.2
31 - 40	75	24.9
41 Above	97	32.2
Total	301	100.0

Religion of Respondents		
Religion	Frequency	Percentage
Muslims	282	93.7
Christians	17	5.6
Hindus	2	0.7
Others	0	0.0
Total	301	100.0

As shown in table 2 majority of the respondents belongs to the religion of Islam with the percentage of 93.7. The Christian respondents were 5.6 percent of the total respondents while the Hindus were less than 1percent i.e. .7 percent. Since Pakistan is a Muslim country having 97 percent Muslims population. Therefore, it is obvious that the majority of respondents were Muslims.

Social Class of Respondents:

Ages of Respondents

Table 1 shows that 121 or 40.2 percent of the respondent (convicted criminals) belongs to age bracket 21 to 30 years which was followed by 41 and above at the ratio of 32.2 percent. The respondents with the age of 31 to 40 years were at 3rd majority with the ratio of 24.9. The mean age was 34 years while the median age was recorded as 33 years.

Religion of the Respondent:

than 1percent i.e. .7 percent. Since Pakistan is a Muslim country having 97 percent Muslims population. Therefore, it is obvious that the majority of respondents were Muslims.

Social Class of Respondents		
Social Class	Frequency	Percentage
Upper	7	2.3
Middle	172	57.1
Lower	122	40.5
Total	301	100.0

As revealed in Table 3, 57.1 percent respondents were from middle class and 40.05 percent were from lower class only seven out of 301 were from the upper class as convicted criminals.

Cultural Background of Respondents:

Cultural Background of Respondents		
Cultural Background	Frequency	Percentage
Rural	168	55.8
Urban	133	44.2
Total	301	100.0

It is stated that in the Table 4 that 55.8 percent respondent having rural background and 44.2 percent belongs to urban area. These figure shows the intensity of crime is higher by 11.6 percent in rural area.

Mother Tongue of Respondents:

Mother Tongue of Respondents		
Mother Tongue	Frequency	Percentage
Urdu	77	25.6
Punjabi	52	17.3
Sindhi	45	15.0
Pushto	74	24.6
Hindko	23	7.6
Others	30	10.0
Total	301	100.0

Table 5 depicts that 25.6 percent-convicted criminals were speaking Urdu language which was followed by Pushto speaking with the ratio 24.6 percent whereas Punjabi and Sindhi convicted criminals were 17.3 percent and 15percent respectively. Karachi city is the biggest city of Pakistan having official population

1.7 million and unofficially 2.7 million different people with different dialogues and different culture as well as background is living and migrating from different parts of the country to find their bread and butter in Karachi.

Educational Qualification of Respondents:

Educational Qualification of Respondents		
Education	Frequency	Percentage
Illiterate	136	45.2
Under Matric	118	39.2
Matric - Inter	34	11.3
Graduate	13	4.3
Total	301	100.0

Table 6 shows that 45.2 percent respondents were illiterate and 39.2 percent were under matriculation, whereas only 4.3 percent were graduate and above as far as qualification of the respondents is concerned.

Therefore, it is easy to raise the opinion that unfortunately illiterate and less educated respondents were having criminal record and criminal behavioral intention into their personalities.

Occupation of Respondents:

Occupation of Respondents		
Occupation	Frequency	Percentage
Govt. Service	7	2.3
Private Service	214	71.1
Own Business	63	20.9
Job-less	7	2.3
Others	10	3.3
Total	301	100.0

As presented in table 7 majority 214 or 71.1 percent respondents were directly engaged in private service while 60 or 20.9 percent respondents were having

their own business whereas 2.3 percent respondents were from Government sector or jobless respectively.

In Case of Govt. Servant Status

In Case of Govt. Servant Status		
Position	Frequency	Percentage
Officers	4	1.3
Clerks	2	0.7
Others	2	0.7
Not Applicable	293	97.3
Total	301	100.0

The data of table 8 testifies and justifies the results of table 4.7 so analysis of data in this table shows that temptation frustration dissatisfaction socio-economics ignorance is much higher as compare to

govt. services. In researcher opinion the percentage of convicted criminals from the government sector is very slim and that can be ignored some point of time while making open comparison is occupation.

Religious Attitude of Respondents:

Religious Attitude of Respondents		
Attitude	Frequency	Percentage
Religious	73	24.3
Not Religious	70	23.3
To Some Extent	158	52.5
Total	301	100.0

As mentioned, table 9 that 52.5 percent respondents were slightly religious. 24.3 percent respondents were religious in spite of their conviction whereas 23.3percentrespondents were not having religious bindings. The above said data reflects very peculiarly

that majority of the respondents there believe towards the reality of life were not clear whatsoever the reason they are holding. Infect every religion in the universe preach for love, peace and harmony. It is also observed by the researcher during research

survey that majority segment of the religious respondents committed the crime by chance and unwillingly against those circumstances in which they were. The bottom line draws this perception that

crime conviction was happened under very indifferent strong motives.

Marital Status of Respondents:

Marital Status of Respondents		
Marital Status	Frequency	Percentage
Married	148	49.2
Un Married	148	49.2
Others	5	1.7
Total	301	100.0

Data presented in table 10 reveals that the ratio of married and unmarried convicted criminals is the same as 49.2 percent. It is being observed by the researcher during research survey married convicted criminals were possessing different logic and motive to words committing crime as compare to unmarried

convicted criminals. It is also observed that most of the unmarried were not eligible age wise for the marriage at the time they committed crime. In Pakistani society males get married after the age of mid-twenties.

Drug Usage of Respondents:

Drug Usage of Respondents		
Drug Usage	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	90	29.9
No	179	59.5
To Some Extent	32	10.6
Total	301	100.0

As mentioned in table 11 that 59.5 percent respondents were not drug user, only 29 percent respondents were taking drugs where as 10.6 percent respondents were using drugs off and on. This over all data reflects the drug use is not a strong motivator

for crime. In Pakistani society the said data also shows that majority of convicted criminals were having certainly different psychological and social drives to commit crime.

Nature of Marriage of Respondents:

Nature of Marriage of Respondents		
Nature of Marriage	Frequency	Percentage
Arrange	93	30.9
Love	33	11.0
Both	20	6.6
Other	7	2.3
Not Applicable	148	49.2
Total	301	100.0

As presented in table 12 that 30.9 percent convicted criminals were having arranged marriage, 11 percent having love marriage and 6.6 percent were married

with the amicable consent of their parents, where as 49.2 percent were unmarried.

Wife’s Academic Qualifications of Respondents:

Education	Frequency	Percentage
Illiterate	88	29.2
Under Matric	35	11.6
Matric - Inter	18	6.0
Graduate - Above	8	2.7
Not Applicable	148	49.2
No Response	4	1.3
Total	301	100.0

As presented in table 13, 29.2 percent wives of the respondents were illiterate and 11.6 percent wives of the respondents were under metric only 2.7 percent were graduate and above frequency of the results

reflects that education of wives does matter positively on criminal behavior in the sense of corrective ness.

Family’s Monthly Income of Respondent:

Income in Rupees	Frequency	Percentage
Below 6000	144	47.8
6001 - 9000	75	24.9
9001 & above	80	26.6
No Response	2	0.7
Total	301	100.0

As mentioned in table 14 that 47.8 percent respondents’ family monthly income was less them 6000/- rupees, where as 26.6 percent respondents’ family monthly income was between 6000 to 9000

rupees and 4.9percent respondents’ family monthly income was 9000/- and above. It is significantly very clear that low monthly income is a strong motivator towards committing the crime.

Relation with wife of respondent

Relation with Wife of Respondent		
Relation	Frequency	Percentage
Friendly	60	19.9
Pleasant	75	24.9
Not Friendly	18	6.0
Not Applicable	148	49.2
Total	301	100.0

Relation with In Laws of Respondents

As mentioned in table 15 that 75percent respondents of the study were having pleasant relationship with their wives and 60percent respondents reviled their relationship with their wife were friendly while only 18percent respondents were not in friendly relationship with their wives. From this analysis it is very imminent that convicted

criminals were having very normal family life which means their wives were having very significance influence into their daily work life. As well as household affairs. Concluded outcome shows status of respondents were very influential and psychologically dominating as per our local cultural customs

Relation with In Laws of Respondents		
Relation	Frequency	Percentage
Friendly	64	21.3
Pleasant	63	20.9
Not Friendly	23	7.6
No Response	3	1.0
Not Applicable	148	49.2
Total	301	100.0

It is observed that 64 percent respondents were in friendly relationship with them in laws and 63 percent were pleasant relationship with in laws where as 23 percent respondents were not having friendly relationship with them in laws. In our culture usually relationship with in laws are treated on respectful

grounds. But cultural variation in terms of values, behaviors, expectation does vary from subculture to subculture. Educations, financial and geographical factors also given different positive and negative impact, in maintaining relationship with in-laws. It is also observed that different discrepancies and deviation in behaviors are present with in laws.

Number of children of respondents

No of Children of Respondents		
No of Children	Frequency	Percentage
Nil	14	4.7
One - Three	68	22.6
Four - Six	48	15.9
Seven and above	19	6.3
Not Applicable	148	49.2
No Response	4	1.3

Total	301	100.0
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As shown in the table 17 that 22.6 percent respondent 1-3 children whereas 15.9 percent respondents were having 4-6 children, 6.3 percent were having 7 and above children 4.7 percent respondent were issueless. Above analysis reveals that majority of respondents were having reasonably large

family size which means major portion of convicted criminals were also under socio economic pressure. Since in our culture no welfare incentives provided or given by our government to needy families in terms of food stamps education and health facilities.

Response to Unpleasant thing in Respondent's Family

Response to Unpleasant thing in Respondent's Family		
Response	Frequency	Percentage
Stay at Home	146	48.5
Went Outside the Home	151	50.2
No Response	4	1.3
Total	301	100.0

The data of table 18 reflects that 50.2 percent of the respondents during their unpleasant happening in the family they go outside the home where as 48.5 percent respondent during their unpleasant

happening stay at home. The difference between these statistics as mention in above said table shows almost 50-50 behavior response with slim marginal difference

Family Type of Respondents

Family Type of Respondents		
Type	Frequency	Percentage
Nuclear	77	25.6
Joint	213	70.8
Extended	8	2.7
Broken	2	0.7
Other	1	0.3
Total	301	100.0

As mentioned in table 19 that 70.8 percent respondents were having joint family system while 25.6 percent were having nuclear family type system where as only 0.7 percent were with the broken type family system. The joint family system possesses

many positive advantages but at the same time hold series short comings, as far as the nourishment and caring of small kids specially those are below teenage.

Family Environment of Respondents

Family Environment of Respondents		
Environment	Frequency	Percentage
Moderate	186	61.8
Religious	88	29.2
Both	23	7.6
No response	4	1.3
Total	301	100.0

Parent’s Education of Respondents

According to table 20 61.8 percent respondents of the study were belonging to moderate family environment while 29.2 percent religious. Based on the above-mentioned statistics chances of occurrence

of deviant behavior is higher is case of moderate family environment. Though respondent belongs to religious family do possess criminal behavior might be due to right, inflexible which shows social restriction and strong bindings with egoistic norms.

Parent’s Education of Respondents

Parent’s Education of Respondents		
Education	Frequency	Percentage
Illiterate	182	60.5
Below Matric	77	25.6
Matric - Inter	24	8.0
Graduate	13	4.3
Not applicable	5	1.7
Total	301	100.0

As mentioned in table 21 that parents of the 60.5 percent respondents were having no education (Illiterate) where as 25.6 percent parents of the respondents were below metric. Only 4.3 percent parents of the respondents were graduate. It is very

easy to dig out that illiterate have serious handicap in controlling the deviant behavior of their kids, due to illiteracy even education below metric of the parents plays a significant role for using corrective measures to control criminal behavior of their kids.

Father’s Behavior with Respondents

Father’s Behavior with Respondents		
Behavior	Frequency	Percentage
Friendly	82	27.2
Normal	65	21.6
Very Strict	150	49.8
No response	4	1.3
Total	301	100.0

Effect of Parents Company

As mention in table 21, 49.8 percent respondents of the study revealed that behavior of their father was very strict with them while 27.2 percent said the

behavior of their father with them was friendly whereas 21.6percent revealed that their father with them was just normal.

Effect of Parents Company		
Secure	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	198	65.8
No	37	12.3
To some Extent	61	20.3
No Response	5	1.7
Total	301	100.0

According to table 22 65.8 percent respondents of the study said "Yes" to effect of parent’s company while 20.3 percent stated “to some extant” whereas only 12.3percent exposed that responded said "No" to the effect of parents’ company. The researcher has observed from the statistics those who said “Yes”

they felt so secure psychologically in the presence of parents’ company. The feeling they express during the survey was directly with sense of protection they always feel.

Parents Fulfill the demands of Respondents

Parents Fulfill the demands of Respondents		
Fulfill Demands	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	87	28.9
No	22	7.3
To some Extent	189	62.8
No Response	3	1.0
Total	301	100.0

As given in table 23 62.8 percent respond of the study marked factor “to some extent” for fulfilling the demand by their parents. Whereas 28.9 percent said “Yes” about fulfilling their demands by parents. It was observed by the researcher during conducting

this study that majority of the respondents were having some reservations in sharing above discussed aspect. This is construed that unhealthy economic conditions of their parents were a serious said back into their personality and up grooming.

Marital Life of Respondents Parents

Marital Life of Respondents Parents		
Marital Life	Frequency	Percentage
Normal	73	24.3
Friendly	142	47.2
Conflicting	83	27.6
No Response	3	1.0
Total	301	100.0

As mentioned in the table 24, 47.2 percent respond of the study I have that marital life of their parent was friendly when as 27.6 percent stated conflicting. Only 24.3 percent of the responded said in life of their parent was normal and smooth. The researcher has extracted an impression that living style and standard 20 years back was very contended

and compromising. With the passage of modernization in technology and culture changes brought very fiancé competition is every walk of life in urban and rural areas. This sangria has created very indifferent complexity in the area of socio economic our society.

History of Drug Usage of Parents

History of Drug Usage of Parents		
Drug Usage by	Frequency	Percentage
Mother	0	0
Father	10	3.3
Both	4	1.3
No One	285	94.7
No Response	2	0.7
Total	301	100

As mentioned, is table 25 that 94.7 percent respondents shared their parents were not drug over and 3.3 percent said that their father was having history of drug use age. It is observed generally

parents of the respondent's were not drug addict nether having drug history.

Crime of Respondents

Crime of Respondents		
Crime	Frequency	Percentage
Dacoity/Robbery	49	16.3
Drugs Related	45	15.0
Murder	120	39.9
Kidnapping	56	18.6
Others (Dispute, Forgery, Sexual offence)	31	10.3
Total	301	100

As mentioned in table 26, 39.9percentb conflicted respondents committed murder while 18.6 percent respondent were involved in kidnappings, 16.3percent respondent contacted dotty rubbery and 15percent of the respondents were involved in drug crimes. 10.3 percent were involved in other crime such as disputes forgeries, sexed offence. It is

observed during research survey that highest suaveness of crime intention was murder. It is also observed during the study survey murder was done in protection intention as defensive move and revenge. Kidnapping and robbery are both highly violent act in our society. During survey it was revealed that major motive behind these two crimes was financial gives and revenge.

Reason of Crime

Reason of Crime		
Reason	Frequency	Percentage
Money	163	54.2

Revenge	80	26.6
Defense	14	4.7
Pleasure	22	7.3
Satisfaction	2	0.7
Mistake	20	6.6
Total	301	100

It is stated in table 27 that 54.2 percent respondent of the study committed crime for the urge of money, whereas 26.6percent committed crime for ravage. It is interested note that 7.3 percent and 6.6percent of the respondent committed crime for the said of pleasure and by mistake respectively.

As researcher has observed during the research survey and already express as well as highlighted observation that majority of the criminals reasoned them salve financial crises, fanatical gravis and to satisfies revenge desire. This violent b/H reflects injustice in the society and uneven distraction it wealth the said factor clearly the cause of frustration, which is a story motivators of community different

crimes. So therefore, socio economic factor is a primary reason for committing crime.

History of Crime in Family Members

As mentioned in table 40, 94.4 percent respondents of the study said that then family members have no criminal’s history. Whereas only 1.5 percent respondents accepted that their father was having a criminal history. The above statistic shows there was no criminal record regarding about their family members. It means historically the fairly in which they belong was a peace full member of the society the respondents squared violent b/H from the crowding environment fall kind.

First Deviation of Respondents

First Deviation of Respondents		
First Deviation	Frequency	Percentage
Yes	236	78.4
No	65	21.6
Total	301	100.0

As mentioned in table 28 that 78.4 percent respondents of the study accepted their offence as a first deviation. When as 21.6 percent respondents marked no which mean they have been committing

crime in the part. Which mean they have significant criminal history for which they were reluctant to share.

Extent of Family Adjustment

Extent of Family Adjustment			
Percentage	Extent	Frequency	Percentage
Below 30 %	Highly Adjusted	88	29.2
Between 31 -	Moderately	116	38.5

50 %	Adjusted		
Above 50%	Not Adjusted	97	32.2
Total		301	100

As mentioned in table 43 that 38.5 percent respondents of the study were moderately adjusted in their families, whereas 32.2 percent respondents were found not adjusted in their families and the rest of 29.2 percent respondents were found highly adjusted in their families.

RESULTS OF STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF THE HYPOTHESES

1. Results of Pearson Chi-Square indicate that there is strong significant relationship between age of males and their motivator of crime. Therefore, we will accept that age of males is likely to be related with motivator of crime.
2. Results of Pearson Chi-Square indicate that there is strong significant relationship between age of males and type of crime. Therefore, we will accept that age of males is likely to be related with type of crime committed by them.
3. Results of Pearson Chi-Square indicate that there is strong significant relationship between educational level of males and the type of crime committed by them. Therefore, we will accept that educational level of males is likely to be related with the type of crime committed by them.
4. Results of Pearson Chi-Square indicate that there is no significant relationship between cultural background of males and the cause of crime committed by them. Therefore, we will accept that cultural background of males is not related with the cause of crime committed by them.
5. Results of Pearson Chi-Square indicate that there is strong significant relationship between family income of males and the cause of crime committed by them. Therefore, we will accept that family income of males is likely to be related with the cause of crime committed by them.

6. Results of Pearson Chi-Square indicate that there is no significant relationship between occupation of males and the type of crime committed by them. Therefore, we will accept that occupation of males is not related with the type of crime committed by them.
7. Results of Pearson Chi-Square indicate that there is strong significant relationship between religious mindedness of males and the type of crime committed by them. Therefore, we will accept that religious mindedness of males is likely to be related with the type of crime committed by them.
8. Results of Pearson Chi-Square indicate that there is no significant relationship between religious mindedness of males and the motive behind the crime committed by them. Therefore, we will accept that religious mindedness of males is not related with the motive behind the crime committed by them.
9. Results of Pearson Chi-Square indicate that there is no significant relationship between marital status of males and the cause of crime committed by them. Therefore, we will accept that marital status of males is not related with the cause of crime committed by them.
10. Results of Pearson Chi-Square indicate that there is no significant relationship between father’s attitude of males and the motivator of crime. Therefore, we will accept that father’s attitude of males is not related with the motivator of crime committed by them.
11. Results of Pearson Chi-Square indicate that there is no significant relationship between mother’s attitude of males and the motivator of crime. Therefore, we will accept that mother’s attitude of males is not related with the motivator of crime committed by them.

12. Results of Pearson Chi-Square indicate that there is no significant relationship between family type of males and the cause of crime. Therefore, we will accept that family type of males is not related with the cause of crime.
13. Results of Pearson Chi-Square indicate that there is no significant relationship between family problem of males and the cause of crime. Therefore, we will accept that family problem of males is not related with the cause of crime committed by them.
14. Results of Pearson Chi-Square indicate that there is strong significant relationship between family environment of males and the cause of crime. Therefore, we will accept that family environment of males is likely to be related with the cause of crime committed by them.
15. Results of Pearson Chi-Square indicate that there is strong significant relationship between involvement of males in drug usage and the motivator of crime. Therefore, we will accept that involvement of males in drug usage of males is likely to be related with the motivator of crime committed by them.
16. Results of Pearson Chi-Square rejected the model of independence and indicate that there is strong significant relationship between extent of family adjustment in males and their crime. Therefore, we will accept that extent of family adjustment in males is likely to be related with the crime committed by them.

CONCLUSION

The research was commenced to find out the social, economic and Family Attachment psychological determinants of the crime and convicted criminals. For the purpose various convicts were interviewed. Most of which responded positively and talked about their involvements however some were not convinced to share their crime and their facts.

It was found that the majority of convicts belong to the age group of 21 to 30 years at the age of committing crime. This also reveals that the peak age bracket is 35 to 40 years at the age of committing crime.

The majority with the demographic constraints of rural resident are found Muslim with their belief of religion later followed by Christians and Hindus. And of mostly Urdu language speaker followed by Pushto, Punjabi and Sindhi respectively.

Majority belong to illiterate group of the society followed by of under matriculation and later with graduate as far as their qualification are concerned. Therefore, literacy and unawareness could be termed as a key factor pointing highlights on the convicts.

Majority of the respondents were directly involved with private service as far as their occupational status are discussed while second majority own businesses, followed by government servants and unemployed respectively.

The component effecting by their religious believes found to be very indifferent for the reason that majority was found slightly religious followed by religious and then religiously bound respectively. It was also found to be having very indifferent motives when it comes to their marital statuses.

The usage of drugs was not mainly found to be the provocation cause behind the crimes majority were not drug user, second majority were drug users. While majority of the drug usage was of alcohol and marijuana (charras).

The strongly pointing factor of low income found to be the key motivator towards committing crime majority respondents falls into the category of income bracket less than Rs. 6000. While second percentile was between the bracket of income Rs. 6000 to, 9000. It further reveals that the maximum respondents were having financial issues and comparatively lower were having conflict with their parents on these issues, and very less numbers were reflecting having other issues. Since the economic crisis globally left no exception to Pakistan, thus the financial - ranges fluctuate largely and inconstantly due to several uncountable deriving factors.

LIMITATION

The evaluation of study is critically important to validate the study as a whole. But avoiding limitations to any study is next to impossible as certain constraints may never be avoided in the real time research scenarios. Moreover, drawing baseline to provide necessary foundations with their limitation would be sure beneficial for the same thematic studies in future.

The research was commenced only on 301 respondents, which was an obvious limited sample because the universe consisted of convicted male in

Central Prison Karachi were 700. Therefore, it was not possible to increase the sample size.

The limited sample was chosen for the scarce and limited time, while the actual universe was large enough consisting hundreds as reported statistically. Moreover, the limited financial resources also limit the access to every angle of the whole space.

The environmental limitations as that of, each respondent has to be interviewed in person with scheduled time where the prison staff has to be present at the time of interviews. It may be likely to have not the accurate response collected due to the atmospheric interference or deliberate deception of the interviewee. Thus, regardless of the hurdle's researcher has tried to find out the best possible socio-economic and psychological determinant of crime and criminals. Information gathered is the study of self-reported nature depending on the subject being questioned, may be prone to some inaccuracy as an outcome of less than definite recall, lack of awareness, or discomfort with self-exposures.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This research, which was confined to only province of Pakistan, may be extended to other parts of Pakistan for more precise findings. The researcher possesses the idea of conducting this research of socio-economical and psychological determinants of crime and criminal among male convicted in Pakistan on a larger scale. the findings could also be made more meaningful and significant. In the light of the findings of this research study researcher would like to make the following recommendations for the welfare of the male offenders and decrease the crime-trends among them in Pakistan.

1. Educational foundations of citizens play critically vital role in the development of civic and social sense with responsibility and duty fullness. Where an individual learns to identify between right and wrong means. Thus, government and private authorities have to contribute in their best to lift up awareness through primarily education. As illiteracy is found to be a vital determinant among convicts.
2. Pakistan is a developing nation, where still more than 25 percent of the population living under poverty scale. Therefore, the concerned authorities should introduce various socio-economic welfare

programs as the remedial policy to reduce poverty, and by introducing opportunities of employment.

3. Use of drugs is found not to be the key but still the significant determinant in determining the nature of crime and causes behind criminal activities. Where government, NGO's and social working agents from the community should put in their best efforts to stop the drugs' availability and by creating awareness.
4. Violence and conflicting situation of social surrounding and within the family may also play key role in generating criminal mentality and motives of aggressive expression through criminal means, therefore families and circles should follow the best moral and social practices by encouraging positively and informing negative circumstances of felonious mean.
5. The system of courts should be reorganized as to ensure the prompt and in time delivery of justice. A better coordination between enforcement authority and courts can help decrease crime trends. Inside the prison, general physical conditioning should be improvised to facilitate the tasks of rehabilitation of convicts.

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